

THE EFFECT OF GIVING ANY CONCENTRATIONS OF COLCHICIN ON WATERMELON PLANTS

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I have an interest in plant physiology and will mix it with genetics. The science of plant physiology is interesting to study because it has many benefits for the community, especially in helping farmers and the general public who want to develop crop yields so as to increase economic value. I want to mix this knowledge with genetics, especially in the field of plant polyploidy which can increase the size of plant cells. When these two sciences are combined, it will make it easier to enlarge plant cells, produce seedless, causes a rapid increase in stem size in plants and can multiply plant chromosomes so that plants can be of good quality. One of the efforts that can be done to get high-yielding seeds is by forming polyploid plants. Therefore, I want to know the Effect Of Giving Colchicine To Watermelon Plants to find out if colchicine can help enlarge cells in watermelon.

Watermelon is a fruit that people from all walks of life enjoy, because of its sweet flavor and ability to be refreshing, Its many benefits in terms of quality and shape, as well as its sweet and natural flavor, hybrid watermelons are currently very popular. These days, watermelons are the most popular commodity, especially children and teenagers. However, the large number of watermelon seeds can worry parents because it is dangerous for children and toddlers. So, I want to know how to minimize seeds in watermelon. According Ranney (2002) stated that polyploidy plays an important role in plant evolution and in crop cultivation programs. Genetically speaking, a seedless watermelon is one with three sets of chromosomes (triploid = $3n$). This can be produced by crossing watermelons with four sets of chromosomes (tetraploid; $4n$) with common watermelons (watermelons with seeds) these have two sets of chromosomes (diploid; $2n$). Giving colchicine concentrations with different concentrations in watermelon can have a good impact on its growth because colchicine can change the morphology of watermelons to be fresher. This is in accordance with Sartika (2016) statement that the Administration of colchicine at concentrations of 500 ppm and 1000 ppm can show changes in the basic color of the fruit skin, line color, fruit flesh color, seed shape, and seed size. In addition, colchicine can increase the size of cells. Colchicine-induced mutations do not only make a difference larger quantity and size compared to the control, but can also impact on leaf size shrinkage (Herman, 2013).

Administration of certain amounts of colchicine prevents the assembly of spindle fiber microtubules. As a result, the chromosomes that multiply during interphase fail to divide at anaphase during the mitotic division of diploid cells. This will affect the development of seedlings and the death of watermelon sprouts. Chromosome duplication of curly chili sprouts can be induced, according to Mansyurdin (2000), by immersing the plant in a solution containing 0.01 percent to 0.5 percent colchicine for 24 hours. The percentage of tetraploid cells increased with increasing colchicine concentration, as did the percentage of dead sprouts. Concentrations of 0.01 percent and 0.05 percent resulted in the formation of a tetraploid state ($2n= 4x= 48$). %. In 0.05% colchicine, most of the root and shoot tip cells were tetraploid but the percentage of

sprout death was high, while at 0.01% concentration of colchicine some root and shoot tip cells were still diploid but the percentage of dead sprouts was low, based on this it is still necessary to modify the concentration of colchicine, especially between 0.01% - 0.05%. Suryo (2007) stated that if the concentration of the solution is still too high low or the length of treatment time is not enough, then the tetraploid will be achieved. Based on this research, it is proven that colchicine can change morphology and affect plant growth.

Colchicine administration can inhibit new shoot growth while accelerating the production of tetraploid cells. The percentage of root emergence decreases as colchicine concentration increases while immersion time remains constant. The control had a 100% root emerging rate, while 0.15 percent colchicine treatment for 96 hours had the lowest root emergence percentage (20 percent). The findings demonstrated that explants treated with colchicine had poor root-producing capacity (Idris *et al.*, 2012). Polyploids, or creatures with cells that contain three or more sets of chromosomes, can develop as a result of the growth inhibitor colchicine. According to Rauf *et al.* (2006), colchicine at 0.1 percent can stunt cotton plant growth when compared to the control. However, the existence of some extra polyploid plants produced counteracted this growth-inhibiting effect. The number of tetraploid cells increased with colchicine concentration, but so did the percentage of germination mortality (Mansyurdin *et al.*, 2002). The benefits of polyploid plants, according to Dounias (2008), include: larger cells, taller plants, wider leaves, larger fruit, higher production, and more disease resistance. This result can be used as an initial reference that colchicine treatment is thought to be effective affect mutations or alter ploidy on watermelon plants and observations were made chromosomes to clarify ploidy what will be done in the research next.

Giving colchicine can increase cell size in watermelon plants, especially in the size of stems and watermelon fruit. This is in accordance with the statement Handayani (2018) that watermelon plants which treated with colchicine have stem diameter and greater fruit weight than without colchicine . In polyploid plants, the larger number of chromosomes causes the cell size and cell nucleus to grow larger. Larger cells produce larger parts of the plant such as leaves, flowers, fruits, and plants. The application of colchicine increased the weight of fruit and the size of stomata but did not change the form of stomata. Sejati (2008) added that colchicine has the ability to double the number of chromosomes. Colchicine solution is given at the growing point of plant germination will cause the chromosomes to double. This is because the administration of colchicine to dividing cells results in failure of the formation of new cell walls. This reinforces the indication that watermelon plants treated with colchicine have changed the chromosome set from diploid to tetraploid.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that the administration of colchicine at various concentrations can double the chromosomes so that it will enlarge plant and stem cells. However, administration of colchicine will inhibit shoot growth. This happens because the administration of colchicine to dividing cells results in failure of the formation of new cell walls. Therefore, giving colchicine is useful for inducing seedless watermelon and producing good quality plants.

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